

PECULIARITIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS BASED ON ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH.

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Abstract: In this article, Acmeological approaches give high results in the development of the professional skills of the teacher. It should be assumed that the ability and talent develop in an organic sequence with each other. Taking into account various aspects of personnel retraining and improving their skills using the acmeological approach, the problems of opening and developing the creative abilities of qualified specialists are coming to the fore.

Key words: Acmeology, professional skill, pedagogical-psychological, Reflex, innovative potential, innovation, creative complex, natural, social, perfection and maturity perfection.

Acmeological approaches give a high result in the development of the teacher's professional skills if: the level of study of the problem of acmeological development methods is analyzed; if the pedagogical and psychological aspects of professional adaptation of future teachers are studied; if the conditions ensuring the effectiveness of acmeological development of future teachers are determined; based on a systematic approach, a model of professional adaptation of future teachers was developed and put into practice. Qualified specialist: it is becoming an urgent issue to determine the possibilities and results of the labor activity by determining the suitability for the profession, psychological readiness for the given type of work, the level of social responsibility, its process and results. Reflexive - improvement of the innovative potential to the level of skill and evaluation of the social importance of innovations, efforts spent, and achievements of its implementation are studied. According to the reflective side: (related to the self-awareness of the person as a

developing "I" and the ability to understand the communication partners in the course of work) considering the system-creating factor, the optimal interaction of acmeological aspects in determining the professionalization of a person provides. It should be assumed that the ability and talent will be developed in an organic sequence with each other. The research object of acmeology is an acme person, i.e. a mature person, based on objective laws, in the process of studying the methodological, technological and humanitarian aspects of professional activity and creative activity, he determines the acmeological problems related to the material and spiritual aspects of the profession in the development of society. . Today, in the development of market relations, the formation of new professions and the training of mature personnel that meet the requirements of the time remain one of the urgent issues. A creative complex approach to the processes of rapid development, the culture of professionalism, perfection and perfection, the aspect specific to national and universal human values in the analysis of the views of scholars and thinkers, and the issues of in-depth acquisition of modern experiences, assimilation of technology, technology and information culture can also become one of the objects of acmeology. In recent years, great importance has been attached to the reform of the educational system in the advanced countries of the world. In a number of Russian universities, a number of works are being carried out on the issues of increasing the activity of people and the social environment. Ultimately, these encourage people to look at education and training as a whole integral system, which lasts from birth to the end of their life, and to put it into practice. It is important to create an interconnected and active system of young parents, social environment and the world of the child. The sciences that study this system are enriched with new approaches, principles, methods and views. The science of acmeology, which studies the phenomenology, laws and mechanisms of human development, which arose in the integration of natural, social, humanitarian and technical sciences, belongs to such sciences. The science of acmeology, which is developing in

interaction with management theory, sociology, pedagogy and psychology, has recently focused its attention on the training of qualified specialists and the continuous education system. Taking into account various aspects of personnel retraining and improving their skills using the acmeological approach, the problems of opening and developing the creative abilities of qualified specialists are coming to the fore. Pedagogical competences reflect a combined set of motivation for independent movement based on knowledge, skills and acquired values. Competent personnel can perform professional tasks effectively and qualitatively. Modern competence includes not only skills, knowledge and skills, but also values and moral qualities. Each educator has a different personality, temperament, and parenting style. However, the approach to the child, his education and development should be the same for all educators. That is why the professional standard set the same requirements for all educators. Practice shows that it is difficult to imagine a modern kindergarten without new information technologies. Possession of ICT helps to increase the efficiency of the educational process, to improve the professional qualifications of educators. Modernization of the education system, like all spheres of our life, remains one of the most urgent problems of today. Creating an innovative educational environment, ensuring its full compliance with international standards is an important factor in the successful socialization of our youth to the rapidly changing social life today. The effective solution of this task, in turn, requires modernization of the educational process as a whole system. In the national personnel training program of the educational system, ``Having a high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, the ability to independently achieve the goal in the socio-political environment, to advance prospective tasks and It is emphasized that the focus is on the formation of a new generation of personnel capable of solving problems. strategies and technologies for achieving quality results, compared to the factors of development of creative potential of a person and efficiency of activity. small or ineffective. Learning objects of educational

acmeology: professional skill and its manifestation in pedagogical activity. a young teacher and the ways of his development and formation in the process of professional training, the developed creative potential of a person and factors of the effectiveness of pedagogical activity, etc. Acmeology takes into account the study of the integrity of objects, seeing them as a productive system, "system", Taking into account the essence of the concepts of "structure", "acmeological approach", "acmeological research", it directs to reveal the integrity and the mechanisms that ensure it, to identify various types of connections of a complex object in activity and to reduce them to a single theoretical basis. In accordance with the theoretical and practical rules of pedagogy, the effectiveness of the educational system is defined as the achievement of the goals and tasks set by the subjects of educational activity, which results in positive results, in particular, the identification of a certain personal quality using adequate pedagogical and psychological diagnostic methods. It creates a basis for the formation of the acmelogical direction of the student's personality, determined on the basis of criteria and levels. The essence of acmeology is a person's deep mastery of every profession through knowledge, a deep understanding that it serves to strengthen the positive impact on the development of society, the development of the nation, well-being, and the economic, political, spiritual and legal aspects of social development. "It is to learn to achieve perfection and perfection in order to spend creative activity, fulfilling one's duties and responsibilities in the field of profession," he says. In our opinion, acmeology is a science of studying the phenomenology of not only the achievement of professional skills on the basis of natural, general and human rules, but also the laws and mechanisms of spiritual and social development of a person at the stage of maturity, and the levels of social and spiritual achievement. In this, we researched the ideas of "perfect man" of Eastern scholars, "Perfect Man" put forward by our honorable first president Islam Karimov, along with the concept of "acmeology" as the object of acmeology, and the foundation of this science is expressed in the manuscripts of

Central Asian thinkers It is not wrong to say that it was found and is widely used in our country today.

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